

A Review Paper on Land Governance in Sudan

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Suggested Citation

Rahma, F.M.A.M., Mustafa, S.K.E.A., & Faragallah, O.M.A. (2024). A Review Paper on Land Governance in Sudan. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 959-964.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).79](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).79)

Abstract:

This Review paper intended to track the land-related policies towards enabling land governance in Sudan. The review utilized, a certain thematic areas and indicators according to SDGs, the Voluntary Guidelines on the Responsible Governance of Tenure (VGGT) as well as the Africa Framework and Guidelines on Land Policy in Africa IGAD approach. The review includes stocktaking of land-related policies, land administration, land use, access, and control. Stocktaking indicated that, there is absence of land policy, outdated regulatory framework for natural resources conservation

measures, limited cross-sectoral mechanisms. Land settlement is based on various approaches including old historical land settlement Acts and traditional customary practices. There is clear a gender gap, where most of policy documents are not gender specific or sensitive. Sudan systematic data type and quality affected by inappropriate land administration systems, capacity for adequate analysis or effective arrangements. Main outcomes which have been defined are Sudan has no land policy, the issues related to land, are well addressed in the Sudan legal frameworks, land policy process and land monitoring mechanisms are essential to ensure land governance and sustainable development opportunities. Key Findings for thematic areas are unsatisfactory, of reforms and land tenure security; and incorporated into cadastral maps with different scales, with limited coverage and inappropriate land information system. Women's land rights are highly insecure. Shortcomings on Land Administration Services, Capacity of Land Administration Systems; and Sustainable Land Use was mentioned. The review Recommended that, there is need to develop comprehensive participatory land policy; Setup of land monitoring system and platform as well.

Keywords: *land reform land policy, land governance, tenure security.*

Introduction

Sudan is located in the north-eastern part of Africa covering an area: 1.88 million square

kilometers extends along the maritime border on the Red Sea coast. Land is a key factor of production in Sudan. The Sudan economy is highly dependent on the agricultural sector as

nearly 65% of its population is engaged in agriculture; on the other hand, the sector is the main supplier of raw material to industry 2019 (MoAF,2021). Despite Sustainable land use contributes to food security, as well as, providing ecosystem services. most of Sudan small-holders do not have secured access to farm land, however, the Malabo Declaration, recommended that Government of Sudan should promote initiatives to ensure that at least 30% of agricultural land is placed under sustainable land and water management practices (CAADP,2022)

Sudan is a federal State where governance structure consists of three levels as specified by Sudan Constitutional Document 2019, that governs current Sudan Transition. These are: (i) Federal level; (ii) Regional or State level; and (iii) Local level. Each level has exclusive as well as concurrent powers as identified by the Document (Government of Sudan,2019). Administratively, Sudan arranged into 18 States, further it is divided into localities and administrative units. The legal framework for land is primarily governed by statutory laws and customary systems. land laws, especially regarding communal land, deny women right to own land and constrain women's access to resources, (FAO,2019).

Methodology

The review utilized, a certain thematic areas and indicators according to SDGs, the Voluntary Guidelines on the Responsible Governance of Tenure (VGGT) as well as the Africa Framework and Guidelines on Land Policy in Africa IGAD approach (Rahma,2022), which include: land-related policies, legal frameworks, land administration services; Capacity, land use, access, and control, and concerns the processes by which decisions are taken and the ways in which those conflicting interests in land are managed.

Land governance was challenged by, inadequate indicators for land monitoring concerning land access and insecurity of tenure affect the land sustainable management. The key assessment

results of six themes of land monitoring illustrated below.

Literature Survey

Policy Development/Reform

Significance of Land legal framework in constitution as expressed and included in Interim National Constitution 2005 and, Constitutional Document 2019. They include articles call for Land Commissions and specify the need to develop policies and laws that manage land use; the Sudan government has taken policy-related measures, which include: (i) Recognizing the legality of customary land rights systems (ii) Facilitating land accessibility through strategic residential plans in urban and rural areas and (iii) Increasing opportunities for agricultural land accessibility (iv) optimal land use map and developments plans and international commitments instruments to address the land challenges. There are very few policies have actually been adopted in the land related sectors over the last two decades. In Sudan the policy, legal and institutional framework to deal with land created during the past century has been rendered inadequate by the tremendous changes in the social, political, economic, cultural and environmental circumstances of the country (FNC,2018). Sudan's Constitution of 2019 Chapter 14, regarding the right and freedom, it is clearly stated that among others; (i.) the state protects women's rights as provided in international and regional agreements ratified by Sudan; (ii.) the state guarantees to both men and women the equal right to enjoy all civil, political, social, cultural, and economic rights, and (iii). the state guarantees women's rights in all fields and develops them through positive discriminations.

Land Tenure Security and Land Administration Services

Sudan Survey Authority (SSA); It is responsible for Overall Supervision of Geomatics activities in Sudan. Development and Implementation of Sudan Base map topographic, geodetic and cadastral surveying and for the publication of official mapping.

Land registrations of Geomatics activities cover most of the major urban centers and land along the River Nile, while the rain-fed lands, which form most of the country's land, are unregistered.

Formal law provides that all unregistered land – which comprises 90% of the country's land – is owned by the government. Only a very small percentage (10% or less) of land in Sudan is surveyed and registered. Urban cadastral information was largely nonexistent or in disarray. Most land transactions are informal and not registered (USAID, 2013, Abukashawa, 2022). Recently cadastral information is well structured in digital format (SSA, 2022).

According to Unregistered Land Act 1970 and the Civil Transaction Act (1984), in land administration services, land transactions cost about (3%-4%) of land value depends on the type of ownership whether it is freehold or beneficial one, for agriculture investment registration land transactions cost 2.3% of land value, however, there is variation according to transaction type and working environment.

In legally recognized documentation, there are no gender disaggregation, however, about 17.8 million of both sexes from the total Sudan population (43.4%) are engaged in the agricultural sector in 2021, while only 0.05% of women and men who engaged in the agricultural sector and perceive their rights to land are protected, inherit right is governed by Sharia Law which indicated that, women and men have equal rights to land including rights to use, control, own, inherit and transact these rights. Despite of that, women's land rights are highly insecure in Sudan. Many community members obtain land through customary land allocations, and the land is commonly granted to male family members. Women rarely have direct rights to land; Male family members may sell or transfer the family land without the woman's consent or simply deny her rights to use the land. In rural areas where customary law prevails women's access to land is often hindered because they have only indirect rights to land under most customary tenure systems (USAID, 2013). The

government of Sudan rates the taxes concerning land and transactions pertaining thereto; tax on leasing income at the rate of 10%, of total government revenue, capital gains tax is % in respect to gains on the sale of lands and buildings, rentals at the rate of 10% for any sum above 3000 Sudanese pounds (10\$). Taxes imposed on goods and services, including other land sources account for 74% of total tax revenues (Rahma, 2022).

Land Conflicts and Land Disputes

Land users from different tribes and ethnic groups shared the land, to their mutual benefits, but continuous increase in human population, food insecurity and displacement have increased pressure on natural resources. There are cross-border conflicts involves current and potential conflicts over contested areas with neighboring countries. Unfortunately there is lack of published disaggregated data of the cases at national relevant institutions. Most of the data is provided by the UN agencies. There are no available disaggregated data or gender based on number of people who have had land disputes and have access to effective dispute-resolution mechanisms against total reported land disputes (UN-OCHA, 2020).

According to land registrar office (2022) even there is no system or intention for recording such data. Furthermore, in addition to courts there are diverse conflict resolution mechanisms such as: tribal, rural customary courts; peace councils; community-based resolution mechanisms; crop protection committees; and locality security committee, there are no specific studies or research

Capacity and Accuracy of Land Administration Systems

The structure of land administration, at both the federal and state level, is characterized by the presence of large number of actors who, although influence land use decisions in one way or another, are not closely linked or integrated. The rapidly changing dynamics of land tenure make the existing institutional arrangements manifestly incapable to keep pace with the progressively evolving national and local

contexts of land administration management (Egemi,2022) .Article 7 of the Civil Transactions1984 stated that land transactions must be registered, but does not set ceilings on permissible land transactions to protect legitimate tenure rights, human rights, livelihoods, food security and the environment from risks that could arise from large-scale transactions in tenure rights.it does not establish a monitoring system for the implementation and impact of agreements involving large-scale transactions in tenure rights.

Sustainable Land Use

the Land cover classes 2021, over the period from 2000 to 2015, the share of forested areas as a percentage of Sudan's total area has declined from 12% to 10% (i.e., from 0.22 to 0.2 million Km²). Wooded land shows a similar trend, from 0.24 to 0.21 million Km² over the 2000-2015 period, equivalent to an average annual rate of decline of about 0.83% per year. - The uncertainty in the tenure system led to the loss in most natural forests leading to a decline of forest cover from 40% of Sudan to approximately 29% in 2005. Wooded land shows a similar trend, from 23.5 to 0.21 million Km² over the 2000-2015 with annual rate of decline of about 0.83% per year. Rangeland declined from 0.96 to 0.045 million Km² over the 2011-2017. Consequently, change in plant composition, and Loss of wildlife habitat. However, the situation was aggravated by, absence of rural and urban administrative units with sustainable land-use plans (FNC,2019,2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Stocktaking and outcomes indicated that, land policy process and land monitoring mechanisms are essential to ensure land governance and sustainable development opportunities; there is absence of land policy, outdated regulatory framework for natural resources conservation measures, limited cross-sectoral mechanisms within line ministries in relation to land governance. Land settlement is based on various approaches including old historical land

settlement Acts and traditional customary practices. There is clear a gender gap, where most of policy documents are not gender specific or sensitive. Sudan systematic data type and quality affected by inappropriate land administration systems. Provision of data challenged by lack of the financial resources. Lack of capacity for adequate analysis or effective arrangements for dissemination. There are no regulatory or guiding frameworks to facilitate data sharing at all levels.

Land indicators datasets was depending on national priorities, availability and accessibility. according to VGGT and IGAD approach the utilization of the measurement themes and number of indicators at the national level which include: policy development/reform; land tenure security; land conflicts and land disputes; land administration services; capacity and accuracy of land administration systems and sustainable land use. Key Findings for thematic areas and indicators could be concluded as follows:

Policy development/Reform; examined to land related sectors water, forests and rangelands, therefore, Institutional arrangements are crucial for land governance as fragmented land related institutions at national and local levels making difficult to organize land criteria and indicators

Land tenure security; national land areas with rights holders clearly identified and incorporated into cadastral maps with different scales, with limited coverage and inappropriate land information system. Women's land rights are highly insecure as many community members obtain land through customary land allocations, and the land is commonly granted to the males of the family members.

Although, land administration services are integral part of the land measuring tools and effective frameworks at various levels; there is no system or intention for recording land dispute resolution. Land administration services represent source of Government revenue, including the cost of land registration transaction and taxes in different forms.

Capacity of land administration systems; governed by legal instrument which does not address or define large-scale transactions. There is no monitoring system for the implementation and impact of agreements involving in large-scale transactions in tenure rights. Accordingly, it is very difficult to measure the proportion of completed transactions with the total number of processes pending for a defined set of types of transaction.

Regarding sustainable land use. Land use changes have led to deforestation and loss of ecosystems properties. However, Land grabbing constitutes the major factor that causes illegal land use.

The review Recommended that, there is need to develop comprehensive participatory land policy; Setup of land monitoring system and platform as well.

Networking with different involved institutions is highly recommended in addition to capacity building, sharing of information; strengthen administration system and Capacities development (Human and physical capacities).

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